

**THE VALUE OF INNOVATION ACTIVITY THE VALUE
OF INNOVATION ACTIVITY**

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Abstract: The article discusses the importance of innovation and the relevance of its development.

Keywords: innovation, the main characteristics of innovation and the stages of the innovation process.

At the present stage of development of independent Uzbekistan, innovations are becoming the main factor of human development and economic growth. The constant development of the innovation process has a significant impact on the change of human and social life. Innovation has a great impact on the modernization of economic entities. Effective innovation activity determines not only the production strategy, but also the strengthening of the country's economic potential.

Innovation is understood as the final result of innovative activity, which consists in creating or improving a product (product, work, service) in a new guise, introducing a new look of the production process or improving this process, introducing new marketing or organizational methods of doing business, creating jobs or establishing external relations.

Innovation acts as a necessary tool that constantly ensures economic growth and competitiveness in industries with high throughput of both traditional and new science. The main characteristics of innovation:

- Scientific and technical innovations;
- Practical application;
- Commercial realization, that is, the ability to meet consumer demand in the market to a certain extent.

In general, the innovation process is the process of formation and distribution in the market from innovation to product.

Stages of the innovation process:

Stage 1 is a new idea and knowledge;

Stage 2-introduction of innovations (innovations) into practical activity, i.e. innovation;

Stage 3-diffusion of innovations. That is, the use of innovative products, services and technologies in new spaces and conditions.

Thus, the concept of "innovation" as a set of developments, innovations and improved tools in all industries (manufacturing, research, etc.), providing or, if possible, creating conditions for their provision.

The ultimate goal of innovation activity is to increase the competitiveness of the product (product), expand its market, increase the size and rate of profit (income) on the basis of ensuring the sustainability of the functioning of the firm (enterprise).

According to the subject and areas of application, innovations are divided into:

- grocery (new products or services);
- marketability (the formation of new areas of use of goods or the introduction of services in a new market);
- innovative processes (technologies, processes of organization and management of production)

The listed criteria for dividing innovations into types make it possible to determine the strategy of a firm (enterprise), develop forms of sale of goods (services) and forms of economic management based on the types of innovations. Any innovation, that is, innovation, finds its expression in specific projects, focuses on specific goals and, based on deep calculations, analysis and expertise, determines the prospect of future results.

Innovation is the application of innovation in any field, it is a continuous process, indicates systematic activity, a clear strategy for its implementation.

The desire for innovation, creativity, discoveries and developments that will be obtained on their basis are resource-intensive in any field.

Due to the fact that production is the main link of any economy, it requires its systematic rise, renewal, the use of advanced methods and technologies, the use of progressive management methods, the attraction of effective economic and financial resources in various directions, i.e. investments.

At the macroeconomic level, investments aimed at innovation are aimed at improving the socio-economic system and improve the general conditions of economic development and ensure the improvement of economic mechanisms. In a market economy, production must have perfect factors and requires the necessary economic resources, that is, investments. At the same time, investments aimed at innovation are mobilized to improve the material, socio-economic and ideological-political features of the socio-economic system. Such investments are focused on ensuring the priority of resources, products, services, forms of ownership, economic mechanism, ideas and policies to which they aspire.

The current state of the economy of our country requires an acceleration of the pace of implementation of innovative transformations in the national economy. The experience of countries with developed economies shows that active, effective innovation and marketing strategies can be implemented only with the rational use of economic and natural factors of the country. The innovative formation of the economy in a market economy is primarily due to industries

that ensure economic growth, which, in turn, leads to the development of the country's economy for processing raw materials while reducing its exports, saving foreign exchange, and increasing employment. These factors, in turn, lead to the strengthening of the country's place in the world community.

Innovation is a tangible and intangible product of human activity resulting from the use of intellectual property achievements to improve efficiency in a particular field of activity, which is accordingly divided into technological, economic, environmental, managerial, military, political, socio-cultural, legal and other types.

At the last stages of economic development in our country, much attention is paid to accelerating the innovation process. In order to radically improve the institutional and organizational and legal foundations for supporting innovation, stimulating the introduction of innovative developments and technologies, scientific achievements, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a decree "on the establishment of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". The decree defines the main directions of the country's innovative development, such as the creation of a strategic planning system, the introduction of innovative forms of public administration, the formation of a modern infrastructure for the development of science and innovation, broad attraction of investments, improvement of the legal framework, support and stimulation of research and innovation activities, active introduction of advanced technologies in relevant areas of social and economic life. the directions are defined.

The decree established the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and defined the main directions of its activities in the fields of state and public construction, economy, agriculture, social development, introduction of advanced technologies, as well as environmental protection and environmental management.

Based on this, the Ministry of Innovative Development is defined as the body implementing the unified state policy in the field of innovative and scientific and technical development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Ministry is the sole customer of state scientific and technical programs and projects, coordinates the activities of public administration bodies, research, information and analytical institutions and other organizations for the introduction of innovative developments and technologies.

This decree can be considered as an important step in the practical implementation of the Concept of Administrative Reform for the widespread introduction of innovative developments and technologies.

The creation of the Ministry of Innovative Development is aimed at ensuring the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of innovation and scientific and technological development. The new department ensures the mobilization of available resources and funds with the rational use of budget funds for the implementation of innovative developments and technologies.

Ultimately, the innovative development path of Uzbekistan should become a driving force of economic growth, a factor in ensuring the stability of the country and the well-being of the population.

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